

Tool: Risk / Benefits Matrix

Description	The tool consists of one or more (depending on the number of participants) A0 printed matrices of four quadrants displaying positive / negative combinations of risks and benefits. The matrix is populated through scenarios cards as data sharing scenarios are generated and discussed.
Why am I doing it?	Taking decisions about what data to share and in what format is often a matter of weighting personal and collective benefits against potential risks. The Risk / Benefits Matrix allows participants to collectively establish data sharing scenarios, evaluate benefits against ethical and other risks, and finally co-design a data sharing agreement.
Which kind of issue can I tackle?	Potentially applicable to all citizen science projects involving digital data collection and visualization.
Resources needed	One facilitator per table, scenarios cards, A0 poster of Risk/Benefits matrix, public space, pens and pins.
Time needed	Approximately 1 hour
Skills needed (Not Required, Basic, Intermediate, Advanced)	Subject-matter expertise: Intermediate IT skills: Not Required Facilitation skills: intermediate Event organisation skills: basic Project management skills: basic Communication skills: Intermediate
How to use the tool	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The team convenes in a public space in a workshop format. Participants are divided across tables, with each group consisting of maximum 8-10 people. One facilitator per table must be assigned. 2. Participants are provided with previously developed scenario cards that describe different data sharing situations relevant to the specific data collected and analysed in the study and the associated devices and methods employed. 3. Working in groups, participants collectively discuss their views on risks and benefits associated with sharing the different data collected and analysed in the study. 4. The resulting scenarios cards are mapped on the Risks / Benefits Matrix, thus creating an overview on the perceptions of the participants regarding data sharing.
Outcomes	Participating citizens will have gain collective awareness of potential benefits and risks deriving from sharing their data. In addition, the overall research team will have built the foundation for a data governance framework that accommodates the needs and concerns of all the citizens involved in the study.
Tips!	Potential risks and benefits of data sharing situations are not always obvious at the beginning. Try and provoke the generation of all possible scenarios through constructive conversations!